

Initial Focus Group

Research: Good evening, everyone, my name is Research, I'm a student of Information Systems, currently an undergraduate, and the objective of this study is for my graduation. I'm doing my final thesis, and I'll present it at the end of this year. The study we're going to do today is part of the research I've done with Research 2, who's my friend from university. So, the process we're going to follow for this study is aimed at finding a methodology that encourages participation. We studied a bit about the focus group, which is a methodology that brings together a group of people who have knowledge about a topic, or a specific theme, and from there, we gather them to discuss certain points. So, today's study is for us to discuss these points, hear everyone's individual opinion, so feel free to express yourselves regarding the examples that will be presented.

Research: I'll proceed with our goal, which is the title of the study. I think it's not so relevant for you at this moment, but we can continue. So, how will this process work today? We'll cover the objectives of our research and also present the examples. The examples consist of code problems we brought from the context of JavaScript. We've brought some examples from JavaScript and want to understand if these are seen as problems by you, if not, and what your opinion is on whether it could impact the things that are being established. So, the objective of our research is to understand the relevance of identifying more practices in JavaScript test code. From the moment we gather here, the goal is to understand what qualifies as bad practice or not, and if it makes sense in the context of developers who work with JavaScript/TypeScript, which are technically the same thing. And additionally, we want to understand the vision and feedback from developers.

Research: And also, to understand the vision and feedback from developers. So, whether you get it or not, whether it's relevant to you

or not, and whether it's more relevant to someone else. This is really about fostering this debate and coming to a possible conclusion. How will this methodology work? I'll explain it a bit before moving on to the next example. Here we have a title we've mapped from the literature, something that was defined in the literature. We have an example of JavaScript test code, and we have a question. How will the process go? I'll give you five minutes to analyze the code and the question. If you want more time, feel free to speak up. We'll keep collecting your feedback. So, let's begin.

Research: This code example refers to the "test without description." To give you a bit of context: imagine you're working in your company or in a startup, or on an idea you're implementing. For some reason, you come across several test code blocks that don't have a descriptive text. Here in this context, we have a test case, and it doesn't have a descriptive text. So, the question is: consider that your test case does not have a descriptive text. How does this problem affect the readability and understanding of the test case? Now is the time for you to share your thoughts. Five minutes for you to analyze the question. If you want to speak before the five minutes are up, feel free to do so. Anyone raising their hand? Feel free to speak.

P1: Can I give my answer now?

Research: You can go ahead and share your opinion now. Also, if you'd like to ask another participant for their opinion, feel free to do so. But feel comfortable either way.

P1: Well, the first problem I see with a test without a description is that if you run the tests and one fails, you won't know which part of the code is the problem. For example, you could add a permission verification test, and if it fails, I'd know what the problem was. So,

without the description, it becomes much harder to debug your code as well.

Research: So, in your opinion, does this qualify as a problem? Yes or no?

P1: Yes.

Research: And, as you mentioned, how could it impact things?

P1: It would impact debugging, because you wouldn't know which part of your code has the issue.

Research: Got it. Does anyone else want to share their thoughts? Do you agree with P1?

P2: Man, beyond making debugging much harder, the test should also serve as documentation. And the moment it doesn't have a description, it loses that value. You'd have to read the entire body of the test to understand what it's doing.

Research: I understand. So, this impacts comprehension for you. Let's move on to the next example. This next case is another one, and I'll follow the same methodology. I'll present the question, then the code example for you to analyze and share your thoughts. Do you agree with the previous points? Do you see any new issues or points in this next case? The next case is the **Anonymous Test**, and here's the question: How does the absence of a clear description impact the readability and understanding of a test case? So, in the previous example, we didn't have a description, and in this case, we do have a description. Does this description impact your understanding? Yes or no? Please express what you think in this context. Imagine you come across a test file with, let's say, 10 test cases, and several examples like this one. Would this impact your workflow?

P1: It would impact it. I believe it would because the description doesn't match what the test actually does. It's misleading compared to what the test is supposed to do. It should be something that explains what the test does, in fact.

P2: I'd say this is even worse than the first case, because the first one doesn't describe anything, so you're kind of forced to read the body of the test. But this one confuses you while you're reading, so it's even worse.

Research: Do you have any suggestions for refactoring? Any ideas on how to improve what's here?

P3: I think it's about the context. The text is clear, it gives context to the test. But when what the test does isn't clear in the description, the test becomes completely out of context. We can't define its context without reading the whole code. So, for refactoring, I'd suggest finding a context for the test cases and declaring the test according to what it does and its context, both within a test suite (when there are several test cases) or even if there's only one or two.

Research: Excellent. Anything else? Any other opinions before we move on to the next example?

Research: This is an interesting case as well. You've probably, since you'll have the form, already had experience with unit testing in JavaScript, right? So, you've probably noticed that JavaScript has methods for logging things, like `console.log`, which is widely used, as well as `console.warn` and `console.info`. We're not including all of them in this example. The question here is: How does the inclusion of logs like `console.log` affect the readability, clarity, performance, and effectiveness of the tests? The presence of logs—does it cause issues with readability or performance? Also, does it impact the effectiveness of the test? If you encountered several

logs in multiple tests in your work context, would that affect you in any way?

P1: Well, in this case, I don't see it as good practice to keep logs, right? During development, when you need to debug using logs, sometimes it's necessary, but when you're going to, let's say, push a commit or deploy to production or stage, I don't think it's a good practice to keep logs in your code.

Research: In your point, you're more focused on best practices, right? That's what you're highlighting. But would there be any other impact? Or can you see any other impact?

P1: At the moment, I can't see any other impact.

P2: I totally agree with what he said. I'm not a big fan of using JavaScript's console logger; I prefer to use the debugger instead, but sometimes it's necessary. And when you have a group of tests, a big test file, let's say, and each one has two or three console logs, that starts to pile up and becomes a huge bloat. So, that's a practice we try to avoid.

Research: Excellent. P1 agrees with... P1, do you agree with... I believe it was P2?

P1: Yes, I agree.

Research: Great. Any other opinions? Want to say anything? If there are no more opinions regarding what's been presented, we can move on. The next context is when you come across several test files, and these test files have blocks of tests completely commented out. For some reason, a developer made this change, and in practice, this test code doesn't contain executables. Would it impact you in any way in this context? So, rephrasing the question as it's defined here on the

slide: What's the impact on the maintenance and clarity of a test case that's completely commented out? So, as you can see in the example of the code we've brought, it's the same one we used earlier, but now it's commented out. Would this have an impact in your work context? Yes, no? What do you think?

P3: I think it depends on the quantity. For example, one thing is having a block of code that's commented out, right? Another thing is if this becomes a practice and then, in the future, you have several commented-out blocks of code. This can become dead code, which pollutes, weighs down, and gets ignored throughout the test case. So, maybe one instance isn't such a big problem, but over time, the accumulation could become a problem.

P2: Man, I think the biggest issue isn't even that it's commented out, but the reason it was commented out. Like, maybe some developer went there and commented it out because they were too lazy to fix their own code, or the test was breaking the code they wrote, so they just commented it out and moved on. I think that's the biggest problem, man.

P1: That's it. I also don't see any justification for leaving a test commented out in your code. Like P2 said, many times the developer goes and removes this test for some reason, right? And I don't think removing a test is ever a good practice. On the contrary, I think adding tests would be a better practice. So, I see no reason for having a commented-out test.

Research: So, for you, the problem is having a completely commented-out test block. Or multiple test blocks, as proposed by our colleague. Any more opinions? Do you agree with each other? We can move on?

Research: The previous context was about when you have a completely commented-out block, and for some reason, the

programmer or developer went there and commented out the entire test block. Now, contextualizing this for you: It wouldn't be a fully commented-out code, but it would have the test still running in some way, while having multiple comments within it. So, in this context of a highly commented test—what's the impact of a very commented test on the clarity of a test case, and what problems might it cause? Would it lead to maintenance or comprehension issues?

P2: I think the problem isn't... necessarily, but I hate comments in code, man, in general, not just in tests but in code overall because I believe that when you're reading the code, you should understand what it's doing, and you don't need a comment for that, you know? My opinion is that when you need a comment because the code is poorly written, that applies to both tests and normal code.

P1: So, I also agree with P2. I think when you add comments, it means your code isn't good. The code should be clear, someone should glance at it, and within seconds understand what it does. If you need to add many comments, it means something's wrong. I also don't think it's necessarily harmful, but I don't see it as a good practice to add many comments, right?

Research: Alright. In your case, you pointed out that it's not a good practice. Besides that, do you see any other issues? Are you sure these are the problems present here? Or what other things do you think this could cause?

P3: In the case of this code in the photo, many people use this amount of comments as a way to document poorly written code, as was already said. But I think there are better ways to do that. So, comments in code are visually awful. And it depends on the nature of the comment, right? Sometimes we add a comment to a line because we want another person to have visibility on something, like, for

example, the code is still being worked on, this line is going to be refactored, or something like that. But another thing is trying to use the comment as documentation, like it's done in this image, you know? It calls a function, and then it verifies something. I think that's unnecessary for a test code. I believe there are better ways to document that without using comments.

P1: And something I thought of here is the maintenance of your code. Because imagine you use another way to test, and you need to update your code. If you're using comments, not only will you have to update your code, but you'll also have to either remove or update the comment. This will add more lines for a possible code review, and I think that'll create unnecessary work in the end, especially if your code were more readable and easier to understand.

Research: Alright. Any other opinions? If you're satisfied, we can move on. Can we proceed then? Great.

Research: This case here is a bit different from the context we saw earlier. We have a test block; you can take a look at it. I'll read the question for you. So, what are the implications and challenges of using the toString method to compare primitive types, which is a commonly used method? I believe you've probably used it at some point in your work context to compare primitive types and data structures in tests. How can this affect the accuracy and clarity of test results? This question is being asked in the context where you have several tests, and for some specific reason, the developer or the person responsible for writing this test used the toString method. So, what's your opinion about this? Do you consider it a problem or not? Does it impact anything in some way? Feel free to ask if you have any doubts about the question or if it's unclear, or if you'd like me to rephrase it.

P2: To be honest, I'd need to think of an example where it would make sense to use that, but nothing's coming to mind right now, man. Is there any reason to need to use toString in this case?

P3: Yeah, I also noticed that. There's no need to use it. So, I work with data structures, and I only use toString when I'm really forced to convert some data type, you know? When I'm pulling from somewhere else and can't convert it, I can't assert or expect it, so I use it only when I'm really required to, you know? So, I think maybe in this case, like in the test example, it's unnecessary. There's no need to use it.

P1: Exactly. I think the problem is using additional methods unnecessarily, right? It ends up impacting performance, using resources unnecessarily.

Research: Alright. Does anyone else want to say something? Okay. So, are you sure that's the point here? Do you see anything else apart from what's already been pointed out? Do you think this could impact something else, like performance, reliability, or anything else? This is just one example, right, guys? If you can think of another context where toString is being used for something else, feel free to share your thoughts. I'll give you a couple of minutes to think, and then we can move on if no one has anything else to add.

Research: This case here refers to the issue of fixtures; I don't know if you've heard the term "fixture" before. But what are fixtures? They're mock data. So, when you have a test that mocks some data, the question is—let's move on to the question—what are the risks associated with using fixtures, i.e., general mock data, in test cases? And how can this impact the reliability of tests? We have an example here on the right, and you can take your time to look at it, see if you spot any problems, if it makes sense what's being proposed here.

P3: The issue with tests relying on fixtures is that if there's a problem with a fixture, right, all the test cases tied to it will fail, they'll break. So, this dependency issue, I think, might be a risk. If you have a fixture and many test cases depend on it to pass, then if there's any change or issue with this fixture or mock data, all these tests will break. So, this dependency issue might be a risk. Another issue is the test setup itself. A poorly used fixture can give a false positive depending on how it's built. For example, if I get a mocked data, I can put anything in that data. So, I'd have to build many inputs to pass in this test scenario, which could take excessive time, right? With dynamic data, for example, I wouldn't have that during the setup.

Research: Excellent. Did anyone else notice any points or see anything else here besides what our colleague mentioned?

P2: What I'm seeing here is that in the case of the data argument, one of the test blocks could change the values present, right? That could happen, but it would be a mistake by the person writing it, right? But it's possible, and it would break the rest of the tests that haven't run yet.

Research: Alright. So, does anyone else have an opinion on the example presented? Or feel free to bring up other examples you can think of. We brought this one to try to make it clearer and based on the time we have. Okay, just one more minute, and this will be the last example. So, one more minute and we'll wrap up. Alright. Did anyone spot another problem? Are you sure what was pointed out by the others aligns with your views? Do you agree or disagree with someone else's opinion? If not, we can move on.